

NEWCASTLE
UNIVERSITY

**Research
Software
Engineering**

2021

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2021 Highlights

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INTRODUCTION

2021

2021 has been another challenging year for everyone, COVID-19 has continued to affect projects in new and unexpected ways. It's been pleasing to see the team, University and wider research community adjust and be able to carry on functioning. New sets of socially agreed upon tools and norms have emerged to make working remotely second nature to most people – a great improvement on the chaos of the first half of 2020. At the end of last year's report, I highlighted the challenges 2021 would bring; transitioning to a facility model, diversifying our activities and coping with changes caused by the pandemic.

I'm delighted with how the move to facility has worked out, giving us far greater control over our work and how we report our activities. The on-going pandemic has continued to thwart attempts to introduce new services or ways of working, and whilst there have been some successes in this area; much more needs to be done in 2022. Greater integration with a range of other University teams such as NUIT, Staff Development and Data Services will help us realise the ambitions of maximising our potential beyond the delivery of software engineering. Internally to the team, we will be restructuring our management lines; bringing in new ways of working to streamline some activities and planning improvements to the way we automate testing and deployment of code.

The team has continued to expand its skills and knowledge, primarily through recruitment and staff stepping up to work on projects outside of their usual technology area. We've recruited four more RSEs in 2021 and the outlook for 2022 will see further recruitment to meet demand. In 2021, the team had a project income of £1.58m from 34 different projects, with a total research value of £47.26m to the University. Finally, I'm looking forward to putting together the programme for the next RSE conference in September and excited to be welcoming the RSE community to Newcastle.

Mark Turner
Head of Research Software Engineering

January

Mark presents our work to NJRO and discusses how we might collaborate on Newcastle NHS Trust projects.

The logo for the Newcastle Joint Research Office (NJRO) features the letters 'NJRO' in a stylized, bold font. The 'N' is blue, 'J' is green, 'R' is blue, and 'O' is green. Below the letters, the text 'Newcastle Joint Research Office' is written in a blue, sans-serif font.

Newcastle Joint
Research Office

February

Our new Research Facility based cost recovery model comes into effect, allowing us to charge on a day-rate basis.

March

Dave is announced as a 2021 SSI fellow. His fellowship will focus on mental health awareness for software engineers.

April

Two teams containing Dave and Jannetta finish in first and second place at the SSI Collaborations Workshops Hackathon.

May

Robin joins the team from the School of Engineering to work on PYRAMID project.

June

The University offers a matched fund for student summer internships, Max and Adanna join the team for ten weeks.

July

Jannetta qualifies as a Carpentries Instructor Trainer, allowing us to train more instructors in-house.

August

Kathryn & Samantha join the team from the CDT in Big Data and Northumbria University.

September

Tiago joins the team from the School of English to work on the Creativity Engine project with Seven Stories.

October

The University hosts a visit from Christopher Smith, Executive Chair of AHRC, and the benefits of RSEs are presented in a wider discussion.

November

The RSE NUAcT Development Programme launches with a Welcome Event showcasing previous projects and opportunities for Fellows.

December

Newcastle is announced as the venue for the RSE Conference in September 2022, with Mark Turner as the programme chair.

Finances

PROJECT INCOME BREAKDOWN

Direct Costs + Estates + Non-Salary

Team Size x 220

In February 2021 the team became a Research Facility, a significant change to the cost recovery model. The facility setup radically simplifies the way researchers cost time from the team, the way salary is charged to accounts and the financial reporting back to the University.

Day Rate

The final figure represents the cost of running the team in a way that breaks even after 70% of annual capacity is charged out.

FINANCES

Income by Faculty

OVERVIEW

We were involved with an increasing amount of work coming from the Science, Agriculture & Engineering Faculty in 2021. Work from Humanities & Social Sciences and Medical Sciences remained fairly similar to 2020 levels, so this has led to an income increase in percentage terms from Science, Agriculture & Engineering.

- Science, Agriculture & Engineering
- Medical Sciences
- Humanities & Social Sciences

FINANCES

Funding Model

OVERVIEW

The facility cost recovery model came into effect from 1st February 2021, and we were not allowed to use that day rate in costings before that date. This means there will be a long multi-year tail of projects that have been costed using the directly incurred model. The 10% proportion in 2021 is actually up on the estimate of <5% given for the first year's estimates. Over time this will grow significantly and be the recovery model used by the majority of our funding within five years.

■ Directly Incurred

■ Facility

FINANCES

Award Stage

OVERVIEW

Pre-Award funding has slipped back slightly from last year when it was at 75%. This year we have seen an increase in the number of requests for smaller burst of work to spend up on unused pots of grant money that had been earmarked for things like conference travel or fieldwork activities. Researchers have turned to the team as a way of using that funding for something useful when the continuing pandemic has prevented other plans.

■ Pre-Award

■ Post-Award

FINANCES

Science, Agriculture & Engineering

OVERVIEW

As in previous years, the majority of our funding comes from the SAgE faculty and within that, most funding comes from the largest school, Engineering. We've seen projects from SNES for the first time and have made a couple of key contacts in that school that will hopefully enable us to grow further.

Projects 21

Income £ 994,826

Research Value £ 24,658,579

FINANCES

Humanities & Social Sciences

OVERVIEW

As noted last year, HaSS is home to some of our most valuable strategic relationships. Our multi-year joint project ATNU came to end this year and has led to multiple successfully funded follow on projects that will begin in 2022.

Projects	7
Income	£ 266,313
Research Value	£ 8,944,384

FINANCES

Medical Sciences

OVERVIEW

FMS is still a growth area for us, there have been some inroads into the different institutes, but more can be done. We're well known to a small number of academics, but we need to broaden our visibility; this will be a key aim in 2022.

Projects	6
Income	£ 320,830
Research Value	£ 13,657,253

The Team

THE PEOPLE THAT MAKE IT HAPPEN

Kate Court

Programming

JavaScript, TypeScript, HTML/CSS, Java, XML, XSLT

Software

Angular, Node.js, eXist-db, Docker, MongoDB, Azure Functions, Terraform, GitHub Workflows

Web & Mobile

Kate is a full stack web developer who originally trained in the Arts before completing an MSc in Computer Science at Newcastle University in 2018. During her time in the team, she has trained as a Software Carpentries instructor and supervised Masters level dissertation students. She has also designed and delivered an entry level digital skills course for local women. Kate leads the Web and Mobile Team.

Samantha Finnigan

Programming

Python, JavaScript (ES6), TypeScript, C, C++, Java, HTML5/CSS3, PHP

Software

Vue.js, Flask, Pandas, Jupyter, Docker, MySQL, MongoDB, Nginx, Redis, Traefik, Git and GitHub, vim

Web & Mobile

Samantha joined the team in August 2021, following a postdoctoral research position in which she developed tools for modelling crop distribution across the UK. She is a trained researcher and full-stack web developer, with experience in a range of technologies and a background in Human-Computer Interaction.

Her PhD work focused on the design of smart building technologies for improving inclusion, through development of interactive systems and research prototypes. She brings to the team an expertise with sensors, data, web platforms, and user-centred design methodologies.

Tiago Sousa Garcia

Programming

HTML/CSS, JavaScript, XML, XSLT, TEI, C, Python, R

Software

Bootstrap, React, Docker, Git and GitHub

Data Science

Tiago is a frontend web developer and digital humanist. Before his graduate and post-graduate education in literature, he worked as a software developer and studied computer engineering in Portugal. Between 2017 and 2021, he was the Research Associate for the ATNU project, based at the School of English, where he also taught literary and digital humanities' focused modules. In 2020-2021, he convened and ran the Coding for Humanists study group. He is a co-managing editor of the Journal of the Text Encoding Initiative and an editorial assistant for The Programming Historian.

Fiona Galston

Programming

JavaScript, TypeScript, HTML/CSS, C#.NET, Java

Software

Angular, VueJS, Node, WordPress, MongoDB, Postgres, SQL, Puppeteer, Salesforce, Docker, Azure

Web & Mobile

Fiona Galston is a full-stack web developer working as a Research Software Engineer within the team at Newcastle University. She has a background in Developmental Biology but graduated in Computer Network Technology. After graduating from Northumbria University she began her career in industry; working for a large technology organisation on projects in innovation, health and nuclear energy. Since joining the RSE team in 2019 she has kept a focus in web technologies but the subject matter has varied broadly, often being involved in socially or ethically impactful projects. She has also qualified as a Software Carpentries instructor and has taught several of their classes to PHD students and staff.

Kathryn Garside

Programming

R, Python, MatLab

Software

Angular, VueJS, Node, WordPress, MongoDB, Postgres, SQL, Puppeteer, Salesforce, Docker, Azure

Data Science

Kathryn joined the team in August 2021. Following a degree in mathematics from Newcastle University she worked in the defence industry modelling the physics of fluid dynamics before returning to academia in 2016. She joined the Cloud Computing for Big Data Centre for Doctoral Training at Newcastle University undertaking a taught programme in statistics, programming and data science before commencing her doctoral studies. She is currently preparing a thesis on statistical topology for random fields and branching structures.

David Herbert

Programming

JavaScript, HTML/CSS, Python, Java, PHP, C/C++, Perl, Bash Shell

Software

Docker, PostgreSQL/PostGIS, Desktop GIS, Geospatial and Mapping
Web Systems, OpenLayers, Geoserver

Web & Mobile

David is a Research Software Engineer in the Digital Institute. The team focuses on delivering software engineering expertise for research projects across the university. He graduated with a MA in Natural Sciences (Physics) from Cambridge University in 1986, followed by a long career in the software industry, including 10 years working as a freelance Web Developer. Before joining the Newcastle RSE team in 2019, David worked for 12 years for British Antarctic Survey, completing large Full-Stack geospatial web development projects in Antarctica and Tasmania. Since joining the RSE team in April 2019, he designed and implemented principally mapping/geospatial web applications for a number of research projects.

Dave Horsfall

Programming

Python, PHP, JavaScript, HTML/CSS, JSON/XML, CI/CD

Software

Laravel, Flask, Docker, MySQL, VSCode, GCP/AWS/Azure, Terraform, GitHub Workflows

Web & Mobile

Dave joined the team in March 2020, and works as a full stack web developer. He graduated with a masters in Theoretical Physics from the University of Durham and has worked in both the open source community and the private sector. He works mainly with Python and Laravel, with a focus on a user-centered design process. During his time in the team, he has trained as a Software Carpentries instructor and supervised Masters level dissertation students. He has also been awarded a Software Sustainability Institute fellowship to research mental health in the wider research software community.

Jim McGrath

Programming

C#.NET, Python, JavaScript, HTML/CSS, Visual Basic/VBA, PHP, Java

Software

MS SQL Server, .NET Core, D3, WordPress, GitHub Workflows

Middleware

Jim joined the Research Software Engineering team in 2020, having spent 4 years in the same role at the University of Manchester. He previously worked in a range of development and support roles with both public and private sector organisations, either side of completing an MSc in Computer Science at Birmingham University.

Jim's projects focus on making data accessible and understandable, whether that's visualising huge genomic datasets for public consumption or providing integration pipelines to transform and publish renewable generation forecasts. He also provides support and oversight to all projects based in the Faculty of Medical Sciences

Nik Khadijah
Nik Aznan

Programming

Python, Matlab, C/C++, VB.net

Software

Unix Shell, LaTeX, GitHub Workflows, Arduino, SQL, Labview, PcVue

Data Science

Nik joined the team from Durham University where she was a PhD student focusing upon a multidisciplinary study combining the fields of Machine Learning (ML) and Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCI), covering areas including signal recognition, object detection and adversarial learning. Prior to that, Nik worked in the aviation and home-automation industries, as well as getting a Masters from South Korea.

Becky Osselton

Programming

JavaScript, HTML/CSS, Python, Java, PHP, Perl

Software

VueJS, Knockout, Laravel, CakePhp, WordPress, ElasticSearch, Postgres, MySQL, SqlServer, Docker, RabbitMQ

Web & Mobile

Becky is a full stack web developer with many years of experience working in both the public and private sector. Becky was previously employed with the NHS developing a healthcare application to modernise clinical practice for the Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust.

Since joining the university in 2019, she has designed and implemented software applications for a number of research projects. Becky is a Software Carpentries instructor and is teaching as part of the Institute of Coding programme. She is interested in inspiring young people and women to engage and seek careers in the technology sector.

Mike Simpson

Programming

JavaScript, HTML/CSS, Python, Java, PHP, C++

Software

Blender, PowerBI, WordPress, Photoshop, OpenGL, PhysX

Middleware

Since joining the Digital Institute in 2016, Mike has developed software applications for a number of research projects, including projects with the NHS and the Alan Turing Institute. He has presented his work at a number of events, including the international Blender conference in Amsterdam, the UK RSE Conference and the IEEE e-Science Conference in Auckland, NZ.

His research interests include the application of games industry technologies for other applications - such as gamification in education and healthcare - as well as virtual simulation and data visualisation. He also has experience of 3D graphics, web development and software engineering in a range of programming languages.

Jannetta Steyn

Programming

Java, JavaScript, Python, R, MatLab, HTML/CSS, PHP, C/C++, Tcl/Tk

Software

Git, Unix Shell, Docker, OpenRefine, WordPress, MongoDB, Postgres

Middleware

After many years in industry as a software engineer Dr. Jannetta Steyn returned to university to study for a Masters in Bioinformatics followed by a PhD in computational neuroscience. She then joined the Bioinformatics Support Unit of Newcastle University for two and a half years after which she worked as a Senior Research Associate in the School of Computing.

In 2019 she joined the Research Software Engineering Team as a Senior Research Software Engineer. In 2020 she qualified as a Carpentries Instructor and has since taken the lead in organising and instructing Software Carpentries workshops at the University. In 2021 she also qualified as a Carpentries Instructor Trainer. Jannetta is a STEM Ambassador and enjoys taking part in outreach activities to make the public aware of the research that is being done at the university.

Frances Turner

Programming

Matlab, Python, R, bash, NEURON, C

Software

Unity, FSL, Docker, Blender, Inkscape, LaTeX, Adobe Creative Cloud, GitHub Workflows, Virtual Box

Data Science

Dr. Frances Turner has worked as a Research Software Engineer for the Digital Institute since June 2019. She first joined Newcastle University in 2013 to study for a Masters in Neuroinformatics, which led to a PhD and then RA positions based in the School of Computing with a focus on applying computational solutions to neuroscience questions.

During her tenure as a Research Software Engineer Frances has qualified as a Software Carpentries Instructor and has been able to develop computational solutions to a wide variety of projects from across all three faculties, picking up skills in machine learning, data science and user interface design.

Mark Turner

Programming

JavaScript, TypeScript, HTML/CSS, Python, Java, PHP, C#.NET

Software

Angular, VueJS, React, WordPress, MongoDB, ElasticSearch, Postgres, Terraform, Adobe Creative Cloud

Head of RSE

Mark leads the Research Software Engineering team in the Digital Institute. The team focuses on delivering software engineering expertise for research projects across the university. He graduated with a BSc in Computing from Northumbria University in 2008 followed by an MSc from Newcastle University in 2012. In 2016 he was elected as a trustee for the UK Research Software Engineering Association, contributing to the transformation of the association into a registered charity in 2018.

Since joining the university in 2012 he designed and implemented software applications for a number of research projects. Everything from the gamification of stroke rehabilitation physical therapy to mobile applications for alerting stakeholders to damage to rock art carvings and the leveraging of cloud computing to render a trillion-pixel image from a vector model of Newcastle city centre.

Robin Wardle

Programming

C / C++, Javascript, FORTRAN, HTML / CSS, Unix shells, Python, Modelica, Matlab

Software

Docker, MongoDB, OpenModelica / Dymola, Terraform, LaTeX, Blender, Gimp

Middleware

Robin joined the Research Software Engineering team in May 2021, on completing a PhD in Energy at Newcastle University. He graduated with a Masters in Electro-mechanical Engineering from Manchester University, and has additionally worked as an RA in Newcastle University's School of Engineering on energy systems demonstrator and modelling projects, including in collaboration with the Centre for Energy Systems Integration. He has also worked extensively in industry, principally in scientific and simulation software environments, and has significant project management experience in both industrial and university contexts. Robin is training to be a Software Carpentries Instructor and to deliver Degree Apprenticeship modules in collaboration with the Institute of Coding.

Projects

CURRENT AND COMPLETED WORK

SCHOOL OF ENGLISH LITERATURE, LANGUAGE & LINGUISTICS

Animating Text: Newcastle University

Principal Investigator

Prof Jenny Richards

Animating Text Newcastle University (ATNU) is a digital collaboration between scholarly editors based in humanities disciplines and the Digital Institute. It sets out to create new ways in which readers and users can interact with texts, and to explore and test opportunities for immersive reading and writing. What's unique about ATNU is that our ideas for the immersive texts of the future are based on the texts and books of the past that we are editing (1500-1900), which were already imagined as variable, dynamic, vital, interactive, akin to a 3D experience.

SCHOOL OF COMPUTING

Auto Generation of Optimal Deep Learning Networks

Principal Investigator

Dr Steve McGough

Deep Learning has the potential to solve many of our Big Data challenges. This has been demonstrated through prior work in such areas as image classification and voice to text. However, there is currently no known approach to determine the 'best' Deep Learning network for solving a particular problem. Where best is normally defined to be the network with highest accuracy, with developers often just constructing, and testing, different networks until they reach a level of accuracy which is acceptable. The ability to derive better Deep Learning networks would have far-reaching and significant impact across both industry and academia. This project will make inroads into this problem domain, seek better understanding of the research challenges and develop an application to an external funding organisation.

SCHOOL OF COMPUTING

Auto NESSie

Principal Investigator

Dr Phil Lord

Students in Computing undertake a range of modules that include code submission as part of the module assessment. Code is uploaded by students into the NESS system where it is marked by module supervisors. There are frequent cases where students have uploaded incorrect folder structures due to there being no validation on data upload. AutoNESSie is a Java based tool that can be run from the command line to validate a directory ahead of submission. Module leaders create config files that describe validation rules to run against a directory. The tool supports rules such as min and max file size, min and max number of files, complete or partial file or directory name matching and a range of other validations.

INSTITUTE OF NEUROSCIENCE

Controlling Abnormal Network Dynamics using Optogenetics

Principal Investigator

Prof Andrew Jackson

CANDO (Controlling Abnormal Network Dynamics using Optogenetics) is a world-class, multi-site, cross-disciplinary project to develop a cortical implant for optogenetic neural control. The goal is to create a first-in-human trial in patients with focal epilepsy. In the brain, nerve cells generate rhythmic activity or 'brain waves'. In many neurological diseases these rhythms are disrupted, producing abnormal patterns of activity. In epilepsy, abnormal activity can often be localised to a small 'focus', which then spreads causing a seizure. CANDO proposes a treatment using a small implant to modulate abnormal activity and so prevent seizure development. The implant provides precisely timed stimulation by continuously monitoring brain waves via implanted electrodes and modifying them via implanted light sources.

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

Centre for Energy Systems Integration

Principal Investigator

Prof Sara Walker

The Centre for Energy Systems Integration (CESI) aims to reduce the risks associated with securing an integrated energy system for the UK. CESI is a unique partnership of five research intensive universities and strategic industrial partner Siemens. The energy trilemma presents many complex interconnected challenges. Current integrated energy systems modelling and simulation techniques suffer from some shortcomings, so models are unable to provide accurate or detailed enough integrated representations. The aspects of real energy systems aren't taken into account sufficiently and they also struggle to generate robust long-term plans in the face of uncertainties. CESI aims to address these challenges by adopting a multi-vector and multi-vector approach within a highly collaborative environment.

SCHOOL OF ENGLISH LITERATURE, LANGUAGE & LINGUISTICS

Creativity Engine

Principal Investigator

Prof Jenny Richards

The Creativity Engine is a web application leveraging the latest technology in text-generating Artificial Intelligence to encourage children and young people to kickstart and explore their own literary creativity. Users will take turns writing the story with the AI, and be able to save their finished result at the end of the process. The text-generating AI will be trained on a selection of archival materials from Seven Stories, the National Centre for Children's Books, in order to produce results that are inspired by the authors' in its collection. At the same time, the app will serve as another entry-point into the Seven Stories' archive, by presenting a curated selection of the materials that have been used to train the AI. The main purpose of the project, to help children and young people to create their own stories and poems, while making use of existing state-of-the-art frameworks in text-generating AI, raises its own set of challenges. Incorporating the knowledge around literary creation and children's literature into the pre-existing, general purpose frameworks leads to questions relevant to both data science and literary research: what makes children's literature?

THE ALAN TURING INSTITUTE

Data Safa Havens

Principal Investigator

Dr Martin O'Reilly

This project is building a system with clearly defined security classification tiers for the Institute's data, corresponding to the government system but extending to research activities. A clean, easy to use, web-based system for management, tracking, review and classification of datasets, and the allocation of users and datasets to projects. Automated creation of multiple, independent secure environments, each configured according to the appropriate classification tier for the data. A cloud-based approach to secure infrastructure means every aspect of the system is defined by fully scripted configuration manifests, and these can be interrogated by any data provider to audit the system. This also provides scalable high-performance computing.

SCHOOL OF COMPUTING

EpiChange

Principal Investigator

Dr. Peter Taylor

Resective surgery for epilepsy, where the part of the brain thought to cause seizures is removed, leads to seizure freedom in around 70% of patients one-year post-surgery. This falls to around 50% at five years post surgery. It is not fully understood why surgery only works initially for some patients, and why this falls over time post-operatively. Using univariate and multivariate data analysis, in conjunction with machine learning, we will learn how brain dynamics change after surgery, and if this change relates to outcome. Crucially, we will attempt to identify which factors in brain dynamics correlate with seizure relapse, even years after surgery.

NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE HOSPITAL FOUNDATION TRUST

ePRaSE

Principal Investigator

Stephanie Klein

The ePrescribing Risk and Safety Evaluation (ePRaSE) project seeks to create a self-reporting tool available to pharmacists within the NHS to evaluate the ePrescribing system used in their trust. Such systems attempt to codify rules for drugs and should intervene when a medical practitioner attempts to prescribe combinations of drugs that could lead to negative health outcomes for the patient. The ePRaSE tool seeks to test these rules by creating patient scenarios that test the ability of ePrescribing systems to flag issues as well as let through legitimate and safe prescriptions. It captures and compares data from all trusts to provide an overview of the state of ePrescribing in NHS England.

SCHOOL OF COMPUTING

FinTrust: Trust Engineering for the Financial Industry

Principal Investigator

Prof Aad van Moorsel

The FinTech industry is one of the major growth industries in the United Kingdom. These companies create new, cheaper and faster services, utilising the latest technologies such as cloud, mobile and blockchain. To succeed they need to gain the trust of customers in a period that society's trust in the financial industry is still impacted by the mortgage crisis almost a decade ago. They need to gain this trust while technologies are changing rapidly and data breaches are continuously in the news. FinTrust will research the issue of trust in FinTech, identifying the generic research challenges and establishing fundamental research results. A particular focus will be on increased automation through the use of machine learning algorithms, which may have implications that affect consumer trust in the new services.

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

Geosciences Centre for Doctoral Training

Principal Investigator

Prof Jon Mills

The CDT is an integrated collaboration between Newcastle University and the University of Nottingham, two world leading centres of Geospatial Systems research. Drawing on experts from across Newcastle University, the CDT is a unique opportunity for academia to work with the geospatial industry to address major global societal issues, such as climate change impacts, urban sustainability, spatially resourcing public health, and removing spatial barriers to social inclusion and healthy ageing. The RSE team support this effort through a dedicated resource for software development advice and guidance to students, ensuring code produced from the CDT is of a high standard for reuse in the geospatial community

SCHOOL OF NATURAL & ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

Google Scholar

Principal Investigator

Dr Roy Sanderson

The Modelling, Evidence and Policy group in the School of Natural & Environmental Sciences need to include data from Google Scholar on their research group webpage. Previously they have been manually updating lists, a task which does not scale as the group grows. This project will create a automated system to regularly pull updates for each member of the group, modifying the data into a format that can be used by the University content management system. Over time the system can grow to include more users and be used beyond this research group.

BIOSCINECES INSTITUTE

Human Cell Atlas

Principal Investigator

Prof Muzlifah Haniffa

Cells are the fundamental units of life, and the human body contains around 37 trillion of them. Most cells contain the same genome, but gene activity varies from cell to cell. To truly understand the genome, we need to understand how it instructs cells to carry out their unique functions in the body. A new global initiative called the Human Cell Atlas is setting out to tackle this challenge, using powerful genomics approaches to define the cell types in the human body and reveal how they behave in health and disease.

```
//is the element inside the visible window!
var a = w.scrollLeft();
var b = w.scrollTop();
var o = t.offset();
var x = o.left;
var y = o.top;

var ax = settings.accX;
var ay = settings.accY;
var th = t.height();
var wh = w.height();
var tw = t.width();
var ww = w.width();

if (y + th + ay >= b &&
    y <= b + wh + ay &&
    x + tw + ax >= a &&
    x <= a + ww + ax) {

    //trigger the custom event
    if (!t.appeared) t.trigger('appear', set

} else {

    //it scrolled out of view
    t.appeared = false;
```

SCHOOL OF COMPUTING

Institute of Coding

Principal Investigator

Prof Aad van Moorsel

The Institute of Coding at Newcastle University runs a Master's Degree Apprenticeship to help businesses unlock much-needed digital skills as part of number of degree apprenticeships already available from the University. The two-year Software Engineering programme will help people who want to start their career in the tech sector. It will teach them how to programme, the software development life cycle, as well as project management and leadership skills. Aimed at people who want a career change, or recent graduates from non-STEM degrees, this apprenticeship-levy funded programme is a great opportunity for businesses to recruit from groups traditionally underrepresented in the tech sector. RSEs are contributing to teaching delivery in Introduction to Programming and Web Technologies.

THE ALAN TURING INSTITUTE

Learning Machines

Principal Investigator

Sir Alan Wilson

In the medical and criminal justice domain, data collecting and labelling under real world circumstances specifically for the application of machine learning is rare. The ability to store data to generate newly labelled data enables models to be updated when data changes to reflect trends over time. This project will develop a generalised infrastructure for versioning new labelled data, so that they can be used to train and retrain models, and keep them updated with changes over time.

Manuscripts After Print

Principal Investigator

Dr Aditi Nafde

The way we read is in flux. We are in the midst of the 'digital revolution' which challenges the way books are available to their readers and how they are produced, sold, and read. Yet the popularity of printed books and handwritten crafts continues to grow. This AHRC Early Career Leadership Fellow project, Manuscripts after Print c.1450-1550: Producing and Reading Books during Technological Change, took advantage of the current, crucial moment in the history of the book to examine the way in which books were produced and read in the past, the way they are produced and read now, and the way they might be produced and read in the future.

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

MERLON

Principal Investigator

Dr David Greenwood

MERLON introduces an integrated modular local energy management framework for the holistic operational optimisation of local energy systems in presence of high shares of volatile distributed renewable energy sources. As part of a 15 -partner consortium spread across 6 countries, researchers at Newcastle University used machine learning and linear programming techniques to forecast and schedule renewable energy generation, battery storage requirements and other flexible energy resources. The outputs from these algorithms are communicated to a central 'orchestrator' via a REST API to manage the local energy systems.

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

Multi-scale Infrastructure Systems Analytics

Principal Investigator

Dr Alistair Ford

The MISTRAL project is an EPSRC Programme carried out by the UK Infrastructure Transitions Research Consortium (ITRC) of seven universities and over 50 partners from infrastructure policy and practice. The project is developing an integrated view of the urban water cycle, coupled within the existing NISMOD national models of water supply and waste water treatment. For the first time, building-level models of whole cities are being used to represent the whole urban water system (waste water and stormwater). This will allow better analysis strategies for urban drainage, such as separation of waste water and stormwater systems, and their associated costs and performance.

SCHOOL OF NATURAL & ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

Mouse MApp

Principal Investigator

Dr Matt Leach

Millions of mice are used worldwide in research each year (EU statistical report 2019). Ensuring any pain or suffering is kept to a minimum requires careful monitoring of the animals so that appropriate action can be taken, and humane endpoints implemented. Welfare is monitored using a panel of indicators such as the assessment of pain, body and coat condition, and the weight of the animal. Traditional methods of assessment based on monitoring changes in behaviour or clinical signs (e.g. weight loss) are time consuming and can have other limitations as they may not be specific to pain or a sensitive indicator of health under certain conditions. A number of scoring systems (e.g. the mouse grimace scale and body condition scoring) have been developed that provide simple, reliable and non-invasive measures for assessing welfare at the cage side (Langford et al., 2010; Leach et al., 2012; Ullman-Cullere and Foltz 1999), but there has not been widespread adoption.

TRANSLATIONAL & CLINICAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE

Newcastle Cancer Centre Pharmacology Group

Principal Investigator

Prof Gareth Veal

The Newcastle Cancer Centre Pharmacology Group work in the area of children's cancer, looking at how best dose infants and neonates with anticancer drugs. The aim of the project is to develop a resource that would display the historical data and case examples to clinical staff the group work with at various hospitals across the UK. Such cases included exceptionally rare types of cancer that only a few clinicians see in their whole career, making the availability of resources and support essential when they do happen.

DIGITAL INSTITUTE

Open Research Toolkit

Principal Investigator

Mark Turner

Software is increasingly produced during research projects to address complex research questions. This poses an acute challenge for students and early career researchers who aren't trained to develop reliable, reusable and reproducible code. This restricts the open sharing of research outputs and leaves students without a key skill for future careers. This project supports the development of training capacity in software sustainability, open research and introduces evidence-based pedagogic practices through systematic cohort-based training. In doing so this will support embedding of this training across disciplines, and fundamentally allow our students to undertake better and more impactful research.

THE ALAN TURING INSTITUTE

Precision Diabetes

Principal Investigator

Dr John Dennis

Choosing the best glucose-lowering drug is often a major clinical dilemma for the four million people in the UK with Type 2 diabetes. The project will use routine and trial data and state-of-the-art statistical methods to develop a treatment selection model to select the optimal glucose-lowering drug for people with Type 2 diabetes based on their clinical characteristics. This has the potential to be used as a decision aid in primary care to improve outcomes for people with Type 2 diabetes. The aim of this project is to develop and evaluate a decision support tool to select the likely best medication class for individuals with type 2 diabetes, with optimisation based on likely glucose-lowering, tolerance and cardiovascular outcomes.

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

PYRAMID

Principal Investigator

Dr Elizabeth Lewis

PYRAMID will develop a digitally-enabled environment which benefits policymakers, businesses, communities and individuals. Our near-real-time flood forecasting and flood risk management platform will demonstrate a new methodology and tool for assessing, analysing, monitoring and forecasting the state of flood risk at higher spatial and temporal resolutions than previously seen. This will enable greater capacity to explain and engage with stakeholders around flood risk than previously possible and will be fine-tuned with our project partners. PYRAMID will lay the foundations for a 'digital twin' for flooding in a single city/catchment that is easily transferable to other UK locations.

TRANSLATIONAL & CLINICAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE

Quality in Organ Donation

Principal Investigator

Prof James Shaw

The Quality in Organ Donation (QUOD) Biobank was established in 2012. This unique resource combines collection of detailed clinical information from virtually all organ donors in the UK with blood and urine samples taken around the time of donation and carefully collected small biopsies from a range of organs stored within a central 'bank'. This has been invaluable in research focused on understanding how stress associated with becoming an organ donor around the time of death affects control of important whole body systems such as blood pressure and glucose levels in addition to impact on specific organs. This has already enabled otherwise impossible research focused on better selection and optimisation of organs, enhancing successful transplantation.

DIGITAL INSTITUTE

Research Impact Fund

Principal Investigator

Prof Paul Watson

The Digital Institute was awarded a three-year fund to support the Humanities and Social Sciences faculty through the application of digital technologies, tools and practices. The RSE team has used this pot to fund a series of pilot project calls. Further funding was then awarded to the team to deliver a bespoke programme of support to NUAct Fellows. Training, 1:1 support and seminars are offered to Fellows, their staff and postgraduate students. This programme aims to support best practice in software engineering across the university. We also hope to raise awareness of the RSE team and produce grant applications that will provide a long-term funding stream to keep an ongoing RSE team financially viable.

SCHOOL OF GEOGRAPHY

Rest & Be Thankful

Principal Investigator

Dr Stuart Dunning

Researchers in Geography are developing methods of landslide detection and mitigation. They have an ideal natural landslide laboratory at the A83 at Rest and Be Thankful in Scotland, a key trunk road where more than £8 million has been spent on landslide mitigation and events occur with regularity, multiple times per year. Previous grants have funded initial sensors and a slope-wide resilient 4G / satellite Wi-Fi system to get data to the cloud for live processing. The crux of this project is to be able to efficiently and rapidly, bring these data streams that are processed in many different languages and software together, and allow them to be used in combination where they are far more powerful.

SCHOOL OF HISTORY, CLASSICS & ARCHAEOLOGY

Rome Transformed

Principal Investigator

Prof Ian Haynes

Rome Transformed (ROMETRANS) aims to advance our understanding of Rome and its place in cultural change across the Mediterranean World by mapping political, military, and religious changes to the eastern Caelian from the first to eighth centuries CE. The programme offers multiple gains for archaeologists, historians, topographers, and geographers by documenting both the mundane and monumental elements of the city fabric in chronological, geographical, and ideological relationship to one another.

FACULTY OF SCIENCE, AGRICULTURE & ENGINEERING

STEM Outreach

Principal Investigator

Clare Fearon

The STEM Outreach project is a University initiative to support the aspirations of young people to achieve careers in STEM subjects. The team hold a variety of technical specialisms and have decades of experience in teaching and science communication. They create a wide range of teaching resources and host various events, such as interactive workshops where young people get to try hand-on science and technical activities. The team have also set up their own Girls in STEM club which puts girls aged 14 and over in touch with female staff and students at the University who are following STEM based careers.

SCHOOL OF GEOGRAPHY

Smart Cities & Inequality

Principal Investigator

Prof Rachel Franklin

This project aims to pool data streams from the Newcastle University Urban Observatory (UO) with ONS residential/workplace zone demographic data, as well as other fine-scale demographic information. Data will be used to estimate 'deserts' in sensor coverage and areas of high data uncertainty and to link with socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of day, evening, and transitory populations. The goal is to estimate sensor coverage of vulnerable populations (e.g. the elderly or poor), to develop measures of "population at risk" for use with sensor data products, and to increase understanding of links between dynamics of population movements and sensor coverage.

POPULATION HEALTH SCIENCES INSTITUTE

SWEET

Principal Investigator

Prof Linda Sharp

There is strong evidence that five or more years of adjuvant endocrine therapy (AET) substantially reduces risks of recurrence and mortality in some forms of early breast cancer. However, many women struggle to adhere to this therapy for such a long period. SWEET will develop and test a support package to help women adhere to their therapy, centred around an app/website which will: provide information about AET; allow users to monitor their own adherence; and support them to self-manage any problems, symptoms and side-effects that they might experience.

SCHOOL OF COMPUTING

Transport Risk Assessment for COVID Knowledge

Principal Investigator

Prof Paul Watson

Public Transport patronage is currently well below the norm, but as restart progresses the number of people using transport systems will increase. This could increase COVID-19 infection due to increased proximity and interaction with infected persons and contaminated surfaces. TRACK will develop a novel risk model that can simulate infection risk through three transmission mechanisms (droplet, aerosol, surface contact) within different transport vehicles and operating scenarios. Working closely with Department for Transport and transport stakeholders, TRACK will provide microbial and user data, targeted guidance and risk planning tools that will directly enable better assessment of infection risks for passengers and staff using surface PT networks, and help policy teams design effective interventions to mitigate transmission.

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

Urban Development Model: Planning Portal

Principal Investigator

Dr Alistair Ford

A new EPSRC-funded project involving Newcastle and Gateshead Council planning departments. The aim of the project is to create a web-based Decision Support Tool, allowing non-GIS experts to investigate a wide range of new-build scenarios in response to government targets. The tool will allow the specification of constraints on building (e.g. green space, SSSIs), as well as the ability to visualise the effect on housing development of new infrastructure such as roads and railway stations. The project will build on existing modelling work done on the Cambridge/Milton Keynes/Oxford Arc as part of the MISTRAL project

SCHOOL OF HISTORY, CLASSICS & ARCHAEOLOGY

WallCAP Database

Principal Investigator

Prof Sam Turner

The Hadrian's Wall Community Archaeology Project (WallCAP) examines the landscape heritage of the Hadrian's Wall corridor and World Heritage Site (WHS) by building a community-based network, guided and trained by professionals. The project aims to foster local engagement and social investment in heritage landscapes. Public involvement is essential to the success of the project and it will be developed and delivered in consultation with project volunteers and communities along the Wall to ensure that activities are appropriate, well supported and understood. WallCAP also seeks to promote a long-term legacy to the conservation of the WHS by building a framework to support volunteers and community groups and help to build and reinforce stronger links to heritage sites/attractions and relevant organisations.

Student Projects

MSc DISSERTATIONS

Dog Training Portal

Liam Carr

MSc Computer Science

Real world project for web-based admin at a local dog training club. In a 50minute class the time frame to mark attendance is short and sometimes missed, using mobile phones a google sheet is difficult to update at speed, the project was to build a web-based front end to allow for more efficient checking in of attendees and updating of any credits for missed classes. Liam built the initial and most user-focused part of this application. He researched HCI and mobile design principles to build a front-end which integrated with the google sheet for storage. The resulting application was reviewed by the team who were very pleased with the outcome, seeing it as much more user-friendly especially when speed, visibility and weather conditions are concerned.

Family Facts Middleware - A Genealogy Program

Qiuyu Chen

MSc Advanced Computing

The Family Facts project is implemented as a client-server application. Qiuyu focused on the server side, creating an SQLite database and a Java API which could be used to query the database. Although many programs already exist to manage genealogical research they are usually limited to Windows, web-based or written in a scripting language such as Python which becomes slow when the database is quite large.

Developing an Interface for Closed Loop Optogenetic Stimulation

Jing Chong

MSc Computer Science

The CANDO Project (Controlling Abnormal Network Dynamics using Optogenetics) is a large interdisciplinary research project based at Newcastle University working to develop an alternative treatment for epileptic seizures. As part of this project, we developed a device to stimulate brain tissue using light. However, the current user interface was lacking in stability and functionality. This project involved re-creating the current Matlab interface as a Java application, and then testing and improving the interface. We hope to use the finished interface in neuroscience experiments and to release the code to be available for other laboratories across the scientific community.

Northumberland Rock Art Database

Dylan Graham

MSc Computer Science

The Northumberland Rock Art: Web Access to the Beckensall Archive website was launched in January 2005. It was the product of a 2.5-year Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) funded project that digitised Stan Beckensall's archive of Neolithic and Early Bronze Age rock art. It included images and drawings of rock art from the countryside and museums. The successful site unfortunately had no ongoing maintenance and the website was archived in 2015 due to security concerns. The focus of the project will be to re-create the website in an up-to-date and secure manner, utilising modern web development techniques.

Human Cell Atlas API Performance

Ming Ho

MSc Computer Science

The International Human Cell Atlas aims to create a comprehensive reference map of all human cells as a basis for understanding human health, and diagnosing, monitoring, and treating diseases. This project looked at a Data API used in an application for visualizing single-cell RNA transcriptomics data. Firstly, the student benchmarked the performance of the application on different Azure virtual machines as the dataset size scale up. Secondly, suggestions were proposed on possible improvements for the backend Python code to make efficiencies in the API performance.

Jazz Piano Lead Sheet Arrangement via Deep Learning

Elliot Hogg

MSc Computer Science

A jazz pianist and music enthusiast, Elliot designed and scoped this project from scratch, undertaking a comprehensive literature review beforehand to assess the state of play in the field and identify an original approach. The aim was to produce fully-notated jazz piano arrangements (both treble and bass clef) from standard lead sheets, typically consisting of single-note melody lines and chord symbols. A Machine Learning approach was used to derive the bass accompaniment and additional treble parts. A sample set of fully-notated jazz arrangements was used to train the algorithm, which was then run on a wide variety of lead sheets in MusicXML format. The results were quite musical and would be useful for beginners in jazz piano.

Automated Extraction & Change Detection of the Antarctic Coastline

Manon Myung

MSc Computer Science

A great start was made last year on the automation of coastline detection in the Antarctic based on remote sensing (SAR) imagery. An algorithm was developed which had considerable success in tracing out a plausible outline for the ice areas of the continent, even in situations where the ice conditions were complex and ambiguous. This year's continuation saw great strides made in both the performance and reliability of the tracing algorithm. Working with project partners at British Antarctic Survey (BAS), Manon developed a change detection tool to easily identify when significant updates to the coastline data need to be made. Further development might incorporate machine learning into the process, allowing expert feedback to be given on algorithm outputs and refinement of the algorithm's performance achieved.

Family Facts - Genealogy Research Software (GUI)

Mengxi Shen

MSc Advanced Computing

The Family Facts project is implemented as a client-server application. Mengxi focused on the client side, creating a Java GUI that would access the server using an exposed API. Although many programs already exist to manage genealogical research they are usually limited to Windows, web-based or written in a scripting language such as Python which becomes slow when the database is quite large.

Training

SOFTWARE CARPENTRIES

TRAINING

**THE
CARPENTRIES**

The training we deliver follows the Software Carpentry model. Software Carpentry aims to help researchers get their work done in less time and with less pain by teaching them basic research computing skills. These hands-on workshops cover basic concepts and tools, including program design, version control, data management, and task automation. Participants are encouraged to help one another and to apply what they have learned to their own research problems.

Training

Workshop Lessons

A Software Carpentry workshop is taught by our trained and badged instructors. Over the course of the workshop, instructors teach three core topics: the Unix shell, version control with Git, and a programming language (Python or R).

Version Control

Version control is the lab notebook of the digital world: it's what professionals use to keep track of what they've done and to collaborate with other people.

UNIX Shell

A powerful tool that allows users to perform complex and powerful tasks, often with just a few keystrokes or lines of code.

Programming with R

A powerful tool that allows users to perform complex and powerful tasks, often with just a few keystrokes or lines of code.

Programming with Python

A wonderful serenity has taken possession of my entire soul, like these sweet mornings of spring which I enjoy with my whole heart.

```
requests.get(url)
response.status_code (if yo
response.status_code != 200:
print(f"Status: {response.status_co
print(f"Status: {response.status_co
BeautifulSoup to parse the resp
= BeautifulSoup(response.content,
soup.find_all("img", attrs={"a
images:
= 0
```

6

WORKSHOPS

80

ATTENDEES

“

The session was more hands-on helping students get familiar with the bash/CLI. We got to explore different use-cases while having demonstrators help us in case of any issues

“

I really appreciated the level of engagement by all facilitators and the time devoted to troubleshooting and Q&A

Challenges

HURDLES FOR 2022

CHALLENGES

2022

Recruitment

The Research Software Engineering community is growing incredibly quickly. As more teams emerge and existing ones grow, there will be fierce competition for recruitment and retainment.

Embedded RSEs

Linked to the growth of the community, here at Newcastle there are an increasing number of RSEs employed in other research groups. How we link up as an internal community is an open question.

Growth

Rapid growth is an exciting but challenging environment to work in. Not all systems and processes scale well; more needs to be done to remain keep the team efficient, agile and happy.

CHALLENGE

Recruitment

Newcastle is by no means unique amongst UK research institutions investing heavily in RSEs. What was once a problem of trying to explain what Research Software Engineering was to prospective employees is now a widely accepted and understood job title and career pathway. Whilst this should make it easier to recruit good candidates who are actively searching for RSE positions, demand now far outstrips supply; it's now a seller's market and we have to work much harder to convince candidates that Newcastle is the right move for them.

Some of this shows up in obvious ways such as salary expectations. UK based candidates know they can get a job in industry for a comparatively higher financial package, so we have to extol the other benefits of working in research as well as the non-financial benefits such as annual leave, flexible working and exposure to the leading-edge technologies. However, financial compensation still matters. A recent job advert we posted set the salary range to the top of the default starting points rather than the top of the grade; the advert attracted a reasonable number of candidates but none from the UK or even the EU.

We experience competition for candidates at different scales. Regionally we are in a strong position in terms of the reputation of the team, the reputation of the University itself and the population distribution of the North East. Durham have invested significantly, and Northumbria are also starting to invest in RSE roles. Nationally we may start to see a shift caused by a change in working patterns after the pandemic. Traditionally competing with the pull of the South East was very challenging, but perhaps more people will consider the North East as a place to either live or work semi-remotely. Internationally it is still too soon to say what effects Brexit has had on recruitment, we've certainly seen higher levels of non-EU applicants.

Finally, the pandemic has changed the nature of work itself – this is a societal change far greater than the University or even the UK. Remote working is now an accepted and in some cases default way of working. Recruiting in a competitive market means candidates are more able to request particular working patterns and flexibility. The University policy on homeworking tries to strike the right balance and other institutions are having to develop policies of their own at the same time. It will be interesting to see if this becomes a factor in interviews and job offers.

CHALLENGE

Embedded RSEs

Pre-Pandemic we ran a bi-monthly meetup for anyone in the University who wrote code. This included a wide mix of people, some academics and lots of Post-Docs and PhD students. At that time most of the RSEs in attendance were from the central team, however there are now a greater number of people with the RSE job title recruited into research groups or on specific projects. There is also renewed vigour within the central IT service (NUIT) to engage more with researchers and those using NUIT provisioned services. Restarting these meetups in a way that caters for these different groups will be a priority for 2022 as soon as regular in-person meetups are suitable. Video conferencing has catered to almost every type of meeting and event setup, but networking style meetups are still a much richer experience in person. It will be interesting to see how well attended the first few meetups are, and if there are loud demands to move them to online or hybrid.

The University has noticed there are an increasing number of people employed with the RSE job title outside of the central team. Even in the central team the RSE role doesn't yet have a defined set of career metrics, training needs or development plans. Including all of the embedded RSEs in the code meetups is at least a start, hopefully including some on the organising committee for it will help give some ownership over its future direction. Beyond that there are plans to provide informal mentoring, 1-on-1 software design support as well as access or funding for things like cloud time, HPC access and conference submissions.

These plans are in the early stages, and we will need to strike a balance between what we can realistically provide for free and what we should charge for. Mentoring, software design support and access to cloud and HPC all carry either financial or time costs that we need to recover. Our initial plan is to charge a number of days per year to cover these services, which we will keep under review as external RSEs use each offering. The needs and opinions of embedded RSEs will be central to our thinking, we want to meet their needs and not impose a service and cost upon them.

CHALLENGE

Growth

Since the team started in 2019, we've had a mentality like a tech start-up would – deliver results fast, expand quickly and make up process as we go. This isn't a criticism; it has served us very well and got us to the size we are now much faster than anticipated. To work in this way requires a couple of things, first that the people in the team can cope with lots of freedom and responsibility and second that everyone agrees with broad strategic vision even if there are a hundred and one ways of getting there. This only scales so far. In 2021 we really felt the strain of growing bigger than our working practices would allow. The main pain points for us became our team meetings, which were too big to be useful to anyone, and having so many concurrent projects to be able to keep the status of each one in our minds.

To handle these issues, we have split into sub-teams and now meet fortnightly all together with alternate weeks given up to smaller teams focused around technology areas. Smaller groups have the time and common knowledge to go deeper into technical difficulties. The larger team meetings re-focused on internal updates, strategic ideas and implementation and technical talks from different team members. We have been using a Customer Management System (CMS) since the team started, but it has taken on a more important role in the last 12 months and is now the central repository of all project knowledge at whatever stage a project is at, from initial meeting to completed work. There is still work to be done to get all the information into the system. Old habits die hard, and people are not adding all the knowledge that they're used to keeping in their heads.

A key concern for the coming year is not to be too strict and overbearing with the use of various tools. People work in this team for a reason, they like to be at the cutting edge of research and apply new technologies. Overly onerous paperwork activities can become a burden that takes too much time from the main part of the job, decreasing job satisfaction. We need to be careful to preserve the exciting and fun team ethos we've worked so hard to build but supplement it with a few light-touch changes to make sure we can continue to provide a consistent and easily understood way of working.

Opportunities

OUTLOOK FOR 2022

OPPORTUNITIES

2022

Training

Our training sessions are well received but we're unable to meet demand. Now Jannetta is qualified as a training instructor we can grow our training offering to broader topics and activities.

HPC

The team is not as well equipped as others at fielding work using HPC technology. That is starting to change and developing skills internally will allow us to help more researchers access HPC.

RSE Conference

Next year's RSE conference will be held in Newcastle in September. It will be an opportunity to showcase the University and the city of Newcastle to the wider community.

OPPORTUNITY

Training

The coming year will be a key period of expansion of our training offering, in terms of both frequency of workshops and workshops offered. Provision of training is historically something we've struggled to fit into our congested workload and have settled on a system that means we run a 20-person workshop every two months. These workshops teach the very basics of research software (version control, UNIX shell and Python programming), and the delivery is well understood by the team so that each RSE is interchangeable on any workshop. Everyone that joins the team is trained up as a qualified carpentries instructor to ensure the quality of the training experience for the attendees is high and that the RSEs all feel confident delivering the material. To spread load evenly around the team we run a rota system, meaning most RSEs only contribute to workshop delivery 3 or 4 times a year.

Despite this system, demand places on our workshops is very high – especially for introduction to Python, which has over 100 people on the waiting list. These are all big challenges that will require changes in the way we deliver training, but there are also reasons to think of this as an opportunity to expand what we do and work with others to deliver a higher quality experience. At the end of last year Jannetta Steyn qualified as a Carpentries instructor trainer, allowing us to not just deliver Carpentries workshops but to train others on how to deliver those workshops. Having an internal instructor trainer will allow us to increase the number of instructors, meaning we can run workshops more frequently to meet demand.

We also get a reasonably frequent number of requests for training in areas not covered by our standard set of workshops. This includes things like introductions to HPC, Docker and R, as well as more intermediate style lessons on testing, use of GitHub and data science skills. To take advantage of this opportunity we have created a new half-time role of Training Lead, which will be fulfilled by Jannetta Steyn. Her new remit is to oversee all of our current workshops, the training of new instructors and the creation or modification of training material to expand the scope of what we can offer staff and students at the University.

OPPORTUNITY

High Performance Computing

Newcastle is part of the N8 Research Partnership, which is a collaboration of the eight most research-intensive Universities in the North of England; Durham, Lancaster, Leeds, Liverpool, Manchester, Newcastle, Sheffield and York. The N8 partnership is an umbrella that covers many activities, one of which is a new EPSRC funded HPC machine known as Bede. As part of the grant that funded Bede, Newcastle researchers have a percentage of reserved time as well as some RSE time towards getting code running on the machine. RSEs from the team are a first point of contact between researchers and the Bede support team when starting a project, which keeps us involved and ready to provide support if needed.

HPC is not something we have traditionally been involved with, we have grown out of a research group that uses cloud extensively and never worked on projects that have needed to utilise HPC resources. However, this is starting to change, and we have made recruitment decisions based on expanding into this area and bringing the requisite skills in to the group. In addition, there is a gap in support provided for HPC by IT services (NUIT), which is a gap we've been helping to fill on a temporary basis until NUIT are able to recruit specialist knowledge on their side. These small bits of support work have enabled us to make new connections with researchers who are already competent coders who wouldn't ordinarily seek us out, but now see value in working with us on HPC focused problems. Hopefully we will be able to collaborate more fully on new grants in the future with some of these contacts.

All of these little improvements in our interfacing with HPC will hopefully grow over the coming year. Our connection with Bede will provide a steady stream of new work and new relationships with researchers at Newcastle and wider involvement in the N8 will help us collaborate outside of our own institution. Working with NUIT to deliver a broader range of support for HPC use will help us be more visible and potentially influence policy or process within NUIT itself. However, to achieve all of this we need to make sure we have the skills to deliver projects that use HPC. We have made some strides in that direction, but more can be done through further training and recruitment.

OPPORTUNITY

RSE Conference 2022

In December 2021 the Society of Research Software Engineering announced that the next RSE Conference would be held at Newcastle University in September 2022 and that Mark Turner would be the programme chair. The conference will be the first in-person conference for three years, with the pandemic having forced the last two to be online only. This means there will be a lot of pressure to provide a good experience, but there is a tremendous amount of goodwill from the community and many volunteers to help bring it all together. Staff across the University will be assisting throughout, and the society has already provided a great deal of support and guidance.

The conference will be well attended by over 300 people coming from all over the world. It will be a chance to show everyone what the University has to offer as well as the city and the wider region. The University has historically been early in its support of RSEs and having the whole community come to Newcastle is a chance to solidify that message and cement that reputation of Newcastle being a place where you can enjoy and grow a career as an RSE. The campus and city will provide the perfect backdrop for a fun and enthusiastic few days.

Internally, bringing such a large community conference to Newcastle will help the team continue to grow its reputation amongst the senior management. The team is now very well positioned and understood by researchers, finance and research support staff. Whilst senior management know we exist, there are not many chances to really show off what we do and drive the message of what more can be done at Newcastle to help RSE careers to flourish.

Contact Us

Conclusion

We develop high-quality software in collaboration with scientists, engineers and scholars from all research domains. The team's mission is to support the transformation of research at Newcastle through the application of software engineering best practices.

Links

research.ncl.ac.uk/rse

[@ncl_rse](https://twitter.com/ncl_rse)

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